

Cheat Sheet – Full Facilitation Guide

Designed and tested by a group of neurodivergent educators and lifelong learners, the following cheat sheet is intended to support collaborative work in the neurodiverse classroom. It is inspired by well-established theoretical literature on building working alliances, emphasising that a well-functioning working alliance requires clarity on tasks and goals as well as good collaboration (bonds). The cheat sheet is a resource for groups already at work – best introduced at the start of a project and returned to at key moments. It is arranged around three phases of collaborative work – introductions and reintroductions, active collaboration, and conclusion(s) – mirroring the idea that different conversations are needed at different points of a project development. The cheat sheet offers conversation starters for navigating goals, tasks, and bonds, including moments of agreement and disagreement. The version presented here was written for a broad audience across mixed levels and likely for a period of longer than a single session. You are welcome to use, adapt, and tailor it according to discipline, duration, and level of study.

1. Materials and Instructions

1.1. Materials

Printed or digitally accessible copies of the cheat sheet. Make sure that both versions are available to participants so they can choose according to their communicative preferences. For participants who find text overwhelming, we have included illustrations that can act as a visual prompt and navigational device. For convenience, we provide two

versions of the cheat sheet: one cheat sheet for each phase of collaborative work as well as a master cheat sheet, intended to fit all phases of collaborative work on a single page – likely most useful for facilitators.

1.2. Instructions

We recommend the cheat sheet is given to students at the beginning of the group work accompanied by brief oral and written instructions. These should cover the following:

- Group work is not just about the end goal, but also the way you get there and how you work together. This cheat sheet delivers inspiration of how you can discuss not just your goals, but also your tasks and bond as a group.
- It is perfectly normal to get stuck at one point or another during group work, the cheat sheet can help especially in those times where you are unsure as to where to go next.
- It is also part of the process to have disagreements in the group; the cheat sheet gives some suggestions as to how to approach disagreements productively. It won't resolve everything, but it can help open the conversation!
- Note the cheat sheet is divided into phases of group work. Today you are given the sheet(s) for the [] phase.

1.3. Advice for Contextual Adaptations

This cheat sheet was developed to facilitate work in the neurodiverse classroom; thanks to the general nature of its conversation starters, it can be adapted to different collaborative tasks and environments.

A few final observations:

- **Repeated use:** The cheat sheet is not intended as a one-off intervention. It can be used more than once – for example, when tasks are being redistributed or working relationships need to be recalibrated. Facilitators might consider displaying it as a reference throughout all collaborative activities.
- **Conflict caution:** The cheat sheet provides conversation starters for navigating disagreement, but it is not designed to resolve conflict. In situations where conflict is significant, additional facilitation may be needed.
- **Language:** While the use of a shared language is advised to avoid communicative obstacles, participants should feel free to respond in – or translate the conversation starters into – whichever language they are most comfortable, particularly in multilingual groups. Facilitators may consider noting this in the written instructions.

2. Conversation Starters

2.1 Conversation Starters for Introductions or Reintroductions

2.1.1 Conversation Starters for Tasks (Figuring Out What Needs Doing)

- I think the task is..., but please let me know if you disagree...
- Do any of us need more information or examples? I would feel better if we could clarify whether...
- I am drawn to working on... , how about you?
- I feel that I am lost. I am not totally clear on...

2.1.2. Conversation Starters about Goals (Figuring Out the End Product)

- So I think what we are aiming for in the end is... , did I get this right?
- If we had to explain our goal to someone outside the group, how would we do that?
- How will we know if we have achieved our goal?

2.1.3. Conversation Starters about Bonds (Working Well as a Team)

- How is everyone doing today? Does anyone need support to engage?
- How do we each work best? What are some of our preferred communicative channels and when are you reachable?
- Would it be helpful to think individually first?
- Does anyone prefer speaking, writing, drawing, or organizing ideas?
- Could we have a conversation about how we communicate ...
- I am troubled about ... (for example our planned / current distribution of work)... Could we have a look at this together?

Is anyone sitting with questions?

2.2. Conversation Starters for Keeping It Going

2.2.1. Conversation Starters for Tasks (Figuring Out What Needs Doing)

- What is the next step for us and do we know how to achieve it?
- Is anyone stuck on their part, and what would help them move forward?
- Is there anything we need to ask the teacher / facilitator / another group about?

2.2.2. Conversation Starters about Goals (Figuring Out the End Product)

- If someone looked at our work now, what would they think our main goal is and is this aligned with our actual goal?
- Are we happy with the direction, or do we need to pause and rethink?
- I feel we may not be working on the original goal anymore and the new one is not clear to me... could we go back to... and clarify...
- A new goal has emerged for me...

2.2.3. Conversation Starters about Bonds (Working Well as a Team)

- Do we need support with the division of labour?
- Is the way we are working still OK for everyone or do we need to renegotiate timings / communication channels.
- I would like to raise something about my part / role...
- I feel ... (troubled / unsure / frustrated) about the group work at the moment and was hoping we could talk about this for a moment.
- I feel uneasy / overwhelmed / in need of help with...
- Can we pause for a moment and acknowledge how far we have come?

is anyone stuck, swimming or drowning?

2.3. Conversation Starters for Wrapping Up

2.3.1. Conversation Starters for Tasks (Figuring Out What Needs Doing)

- Is there anything from today's exercise / discussion that still feels unclear / undone?
- What should we report back to the whole class / group and how will we do this? Who will take the lead on presenting?
- What are the main ideas / learnings from this work?
- I feel that we need to start wrapping up ... what could help with this?

2.3.2. Conversation Starters about Goals (Figuring Out the End Product)

- Let's go over our goals again. Are we happy with what has been achieved? What did not work and why?
- If we had to share one insight with the class, what would it be?
- What are each of us taking away from this experience / group work?

2.3.3. Conversation Starters about Bonds (Working Well as a Team)

- How did working together feel? Is there anything that worked well or anything that could have gone better?
- Did anyone's contribution help you think differently?
- Retrospectively I feel we could have handled ... better, could we discuss what could be learned from that?
- Thank you for this experience, I learned a lot.

Cheat Sheet – Overview for Facilitators

	Starting / Reintroductions	Keeping It Going	Wrapping Up
Tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ I think the task is..., but please let me know if you disagree...” “ Do any of us need more information or examples?” “ I would feel better if we could clarify whether...” “ I am drawn to working on..., how about you?” “ I feel that I am lost. I am not totally clear on...” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ What is the next step for us, and do we know how to achieve it?” “ Is anyone stuck on their part, and what would help them move forward?” “ Is there anything we need to ask the teacher / facilitator / another group about?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ Is there anything from today’s exercise/discussion that still feels unclear or undone?” “ What should we report back to the class/group, and how will we do this?” “ Who will take the lead on presenting?” “ What are the main ideas/learnings from this work?” “ I feel that we need to start wrapping up... what could help with this?”
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ So I think what we are aiming for in the end is..., did I get this right?” “ If we had to explain our goal to someone outside the group, how would we do that?” “ How will we know if we have achieved our goal?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ If someone looked at our work now, what would they think our main goal is — and is this aligned with our actual goal?” “ Are we happy with the direction, or do we need to pause and rethink?” “ I feel we may not be working on the original goal anymore and the new one is not clear to me... could we go back to... and clarify...” “ A new goal has emerged for me...” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ Let’s go over our goals again. Are we happy with what has been achieved?” “ What did not work, and why?” “ If we had to share one insight with the class, what would it be?” “ What is each of us taking away from this experience/group work?”
Bonds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ How is everyone doing today? Does anyone need support to engage?” “ How do we each work best? What are our preferred communication channels, and when are you reachable?” “ Would it help to think individually first? Does anyone prefer speaking, writing, drawing, or organising ideas?” “ Could we have a conversation about how we communicate...” “ I am troubled about... (for example our planned/current distribution of work)... could we look at this together?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ Do we need support with the division of labour?” “ Is the way we are working still OK for everyone, or do we need to renegotiate timings/communication channels?” “ I would like to raise something about my part/role...” “ I feel ... (troubled/unsure/frustrated) about the group work at the moment — could we talk about this?” “ I feel uneasy/overwhelmed/in need of help with...” “ Can we pause for a moment and acknowledge how far we’ve come?” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “ How did working together feel?” “ Is there anything that worked well, or anything that could have gone better?” “ Did anyone’s contribution help you think differently?” “ Retrospectively, I feel we could have handled... better — could we discuss what we might learn from that?” “ Thank you for this experience — I learned a lot.”